

ISic4388

Honorific inscription for Valerius Licinius Licinianus as Caesar

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

marble

Object

tablet

Editor

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Autopsy

No autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Halaesa

Place of origin (modern)

near Castel di Tusa

Provenance

Found in 1970 during excavations in the agora, in the area of the rooms along the rear wall of the west portico

Coordinates

37.997942, 14.262594

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Halaesa, Antiquarium e sito archeologico di Halaesa

Physical Description

A heavily damaged marble slab, of which 30 fragments survive, floated into a reconstruction on a panel. Most of the right side, much of the upper edge and parts of the left edge are preserved, but the lower edge is entirely lost and there are substantial lacunae throughout the text.

Dimensions

Height 58 cm

Width 54 cm

Depth cm

Layout

Remains of 8 lines of Latin text are visible. The text is centred on the stone, with some words split across lines. At least some line ends (and the end of the text) appear to be marked by elegant hederæ.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Somewhat unevenly spaced deep, simply cut letters, with strong terminations and a relatively broad and square form. A has a leftward descending oblique bar; M has all four bars off vertical, the midpoint descending fully to the line; E has a shorter mid-bar.

Letter heights:

Line 1: 40-42 mm

Line 2: 45 mm

Line 3: 35 mm

Line 4: 40 mm

Line 5: 35 mm

Line 6: 37 mm

Line 7: 36 mm

Line 8: 40 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation: not measured mm

Text

1. V(alerio) [Li]cinio
2. [---]L[icinia]no
3. [nob]i,l,i,s,s,i,m[o]
4. [---]Caesa[ri]
5. [res p(ublica)] Halaesi
6. no[ru]m devota
7. numi[ni maie]
8. [s]tatique [eius]

Apparatus

Text of Scibona 2017 no.23 modified by comparison with photograph

Scibona: V. [LIC]INIO

Scibona: LICINIA]NO

Scibona: NOBIL]I[S]SIMO

Scibona: CAESA[RI]

Scibona: [RES. P.] HALAESI

Scibona: NUMI[NI MAIE]

Translation (en)

To Valerius Licinius Licinianus, most noble Caesar, the Res Publica of the people of Halaesa (set this up), vowed to his divine power and majesty

Translation (it)

A Valerio Licinio Liciniano nobilissimo Cesare la Res Publica del popolo di Halaesa (dedica questa), devota al suo potere divino ed alla sua maestà

Commentary

The abbreviation Res P(ublica) in line 5 is adopted as the form used on other examples from Halaesa (ISic3587 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic3587>] and ISic3590 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic3590>])

Scibona offers a clear rationale for assuming that this refers to Valerius Licinius Licinianus the young, son of the Augustus of 308-324, and himself Caesar between 317 and his death, aged 11, in 326 AD.

ISic0026 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0026>] from Palermo is a dedication to Valerius Licinianus the elder, before 314 AD.

Digital identifiers:

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Bibliography

Scibona, Giacomo 2017. Epigraphica Halaesina II. In Mellusi, Giovan Giuseppe, Moscheo, Rosario(eds.), *KTHMA ES AIEI. Studi e ricordi in memoria di Giacomo Scibona*. Messina. pp. 627-671. At 667 no.23

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Photo Sopr. BBCCA di Messina